

Flow Through Porous Medium. Part-VI : Permeability Studies of Water and Ammonium Salt Solutions Through Soil Membrane

R. L. BLOKHRA*, S. CHAND and R. SIDHU

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 005

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The phenomenological permeation coefficients for water and aqueous solutions of ammonium nitrate, ammonium sulphate, ammonium phosphate at different concentrations and at 35° were determined for a soil membrane of known thickness and water content. The results have been interpreted in terms of the principles of non-equilibrium thermodynamics. It has been found that the permeation coefficient for water is higher than that of the ammonium salt solutions. Frictional coefficient between membrane matrix and water has been evaluated and its dependence upon the solute concentration has also been discussed. The effect of concentration of the electrolyte solution on the radius of pore of the membrane equilibrated with the electrolyte solution has also been discussed.

STUDIES involving electrolyte and non-electrolyte solutions have been made by a number of investigators¹⁻⁷ on transport through different types of diaphragms, both theoretically and experimentally, from different angles using thermodynamics of irreversible processes. But a survey of literature shows that the application of irreversible thermodynamics to the rate processes encountered in soil systems is only of recent origin. Flow through soil membranes has been actively studied because of their importance in various processes such as nutrient movement, desalination, leaching, soil stabilization etc. These transport processes not only characterise⁸ the membrane in terms of its effective cross-sectional area, radius and number of pores but also characterise the system as a whole in terms of a set of experimentally accessible phenomenological coefficients. Moreover, these processes help us to elucidate the structure⁸ of compounds by determining permeant-membrane and membrane-permeant interactions estimated from the excess values of these phenomenological coefficients⁷. Spiegler⁹ made an attempt to translate the phenomenological permeation coefficients, used in the thermodynamic description of permeation through membranes, into frictional terms and this approach was extended by Kedem and Katchalsky¹⁰, who derived a set of equations in which the phenomenological permeation coefficients are expressed as explicit functions of frictional coefficients as well as of some membrane characteristics such as membrane thickness, water content and tortuosity of capillaries. The present investigations have been carried out with a soil membrane using different liquids in order to test the validity of the theory of thermodynamics of irreversible process in soil systems.

Experimental

Electrolytes: Ammonium nitrate, ammonium sulphate and ammonium phosphate were used in

the present investigations. The electrolytes were of G.R. grade and were used as such without further purification after drying over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. Distilled water, distilled thrice over alkaline KMnO_4 , was used in the present investigations. The conductivity of the water so prepared was of the order of 10^{-8} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Membrane: Known amounts (8 g) of soil, collected from Simla Hills at a height of 7000 ft above mean sea level in Himachal Pradesh, were supported in a burette. Conductivity water was then allowed to percolate through the column of the soil for a number of days in order to remove washable impurities. After this, the soil was dried in vacuum oven at 100° and transferred to the apparatus (Fig. 1). Here the soil was supported over a glass wool plug. Now the soil was pressed mechanically with the help of a glass rod flattened at the ends. A glass wool pad was then placed at the top of the bed of the soil. Conductivity water was allowed to pass through the soil until constant flow rate was observed in the capillary tube of the apparatus. The constant flow was obtained after a lapse of four days. This is natural because clay is smectitic and, therefore, the soil sample swells on treatment with water and the aqueous salt solution used. The membrane so prepared was 3 cm in thickness and 1.83 cm in diameter.

Apparatus and methods: The apparatus used for this purpose is depicted in Fig. 1. It consists of a 6 cm long pyrex glass tube A having a standard female joint B at its upper end and a standard male joint C at its lower end. A capillary tube D is sealed at the joint C, whereas a reservoir R is connected to the joint B through a polythene tube T having a standard male joint E at its lower end. The reservoir is movable and can be set at any position to maintain the desired pressure gradient in the system. The whole apparatus was kept in a thermostat and all the measurements were made

Fig. 1. Apparatus for the measurement of hydrodynamic permeability.

at 35°. The temperature was kept constant with the help of a toluene-mercury thermoregulator and an electronic relay.

To measure the flow of water due to a pressure gradient across the membrane, the apparatus was filled with conductivity water and was kept as such overnight so as to saturate the soil membrane completely. Now a constant known magnitude of pressure gradient, say 10 cm, was imposed by maintaining a constant difference in the level of the liquid across it. The ensuing hydrodynamic volumetric flux was measured by following the displacement of the liquid meniscus in the horizontally placed graduated capillary tube with the help of a cathetometer sensitive to 0.001 cm. The time was recorded with the help of a stopwatch reading correctly up to 0.1 second. Changes in the volumetric flux of the liquid were determined correct to 0.48 microlitre by observing the level of liquid in the capillary tube with the help of the cathetometer. The reading was repeated four times and the mean value of the volumetric flux was calculated. Now the experiment was performed at other pressure gradients say 15, 20, 25 and 30 cm of the permeant across the membrane. Measurements of volumetric flux through the membrane for various electrolyte solutions of different concentrations at different pressure differences were also made. Densities of different solutions were determined with the help of a bicapillary pycnometer.

Conductance of the membrane and the specific conductivity of the permeant were determined by means of a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at 50 cycles/sec. Viscosities of the ammonium salt solutions were determined by the suspended level type viscometer.

Results and Discussion

According to the theory of thermodynamics of irreversible processes, the dissipation function, ϕ ,

for the transport process through a membrane under the simultaneous action of the gradients of pressure and concentration is given by Lakshminarayanaiah¹¹ :

$$\phi = J_V \Delta P + J_D \Delta \pi \quad \dots (1)$$

where J_V is the volumetric flux ; J_D , the relative velocity of solute to that of solvent and bears a similarity to the ordinary diffusional flux. ΔP and $\Delta \pi$ are the pressure and concentration gradients respectively across the membrane.

The phenomenological equations relating the flows and forces defined by relation (1) are :

$$J_V = L_P \Delta P + L_{PD} \Delta \pi \quad \dots (2)$$

$$J_D = L_{DP} \Delta P + L_D \Delta \pi \quad \dots (3)$$

L_P , L_{PD} , L_{DP} and L_D are the phenomenological coefficients and represent the different properties of the membrane.

For this system, the Onsager's reciprocity relationship is

$$L_{PD} = L_{DP} \quad \dots (4)$$

The significance of relations (2) and (3) can be tested by the examination of different physical situations. Let us consider an experiment in which the concentration of the solute is the same on both the sides of the membrane, so that $\Delta \pi = 0$. If a pressure gradient is maintained, there will exist a volume flow, J_V . The values of volume flow of water and aqueous solutions of ammonium salts through the soil membrane are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1—PERMEABILITY DATA FOR WATER AT DIFFERENT PRESSURE DIFFERENCES AND AT 35°

ΔP (cm of permeant)	$J_V \times 10^4$ (cm. sec ⁻¹)
10	1.21
15	1.55
20	1.95
25	2.43
30	2.98

When the concentration of the solute is the same on both the sides of the membrane the volume flow, J_V , will be given as :

$$J_V = L_P \Delta P \quad \dots (5)$$

where L_P is the permeability of the membrane for the fluid. L_P has a character of mobility and represents the velocity of fluid through the membrane per unit pressure difference across the membrane. The values of L_P for water and ammonium salt solutions have been estimated from the plots between J_V and ΔP and recorded in Table 3. The plots representing the variation of J_V with ΔP for different fluids are given in Fig. 2.

TABLE 2—PERMEABILITY DATA OF DIFFERENT AMMONIUM SALT SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AT DIFFERENT PRESSURE DIFFERENCES AND AT 35°

ΔP (cm. of permeant)	$J_v \times 10^4$ (cm. sec ⁻¹)					
	0.005M	0.01M	0.02M	0.04M	0.06M	0.08M
Ammonium nitrate						
10	0.64	0.58	0.55	0.53	0.51	0.49
15	0.96	0.83	0.78	0.73	0.72	0.67
20	1.35	1.01	0.96	0.88	0.84	0.82
25	1.74	1.24	1.16	1.09	1.02	0.99
30	2.56	1.67	1.54	1.41	1.31	1.24
Ammonium sulphate						
10	0.60	0.51	0.49	0.47	0.46	0.44
15	0.87	0.69	0.65	0.62	0.59	0.56
20	1.15	0.94	0.86	0.82	0.77	0.73
25	1.49	1.21	1.11	1.06	1.01	0.97
30	1.98	1.50	1.42	1.32	1.22	1.14
Ammonium phosphate						
10	0.47	0.44	0.43	0.41	0.40	0.39
15	0.79	0.62	0.57	0.55	0.54	0.53
20	1.02	0.89	0.84	0.82	0.79	0.76
25	1.25	1.09	1.08	1.06	1.02	0.97
30	1.43	1.36	1.25	1.21	1.19	1.11

TABLE 3—MECHANICAL FILTRATION COEFFICIENT, L_P , OF SOIL MEMBRANE FOR WATER AND AMMONIUM SALT SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT 35°

Concentration (mol. l ⁻¹)	$L_P \times 10^8$ (cm ² .S ⁻¹ dyn ⁻¹)			
	Water	NH ₄ NO ₃	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	(NH ₄) ₃ PO ₄
Water	1.025			
Salt				
0.005	0.72	0.61	0.51	
0.01	0.58	0.49	0.47	
0.02	0.53	0.46	0.44	
0.04	0.48	0.43	0.43	
0.06	0.45	0.41	0.41	
0.08	0.43	0.39	0.38	

This decrease is attributed¹² to the increase in the radii of the anions namely, PO₄³⁻ (2.38 Å) > SO₄²⁻ (2.30 Å) > NO₃⁻ (1.89 Å). From Table 3 it is evident that the permeability of the different fluids at 35° through the soil membrane varies in the order :

On translating the thermodynamic coefficients into frictional coefficients, it has been found that L_P can be related to the coefficient of friction between water and the membrane matrix, f_{wm} , by the relation¹³ :

$$L_P = \frac{\phi_w \bar{V}_w}{f_{wm} \delta} \quad \dots (6)$$

where ϕ_w is the water content of the wet membrane and is expressed as the volume fraction of water of the total membrane volume. It is numerically identical with the fraction of the membrane surface available for the permeation of water-soluble substances¹⁴ and plays an important role in subsequent calculations. The volume fraction of water of the membrane is its characteristics and has been determined in the present case by the method described by Ginzburg and Katchalsky¹⁴. $\bar{V}_w$ is the partial molar volume of water and δ is the thickness of the membrane. Substituting the values of ϕ_w , $\bar{V}_w$, L_P and δ for the membrane, f_{wm} can be calculated using eq. (6). The values of the frictional coefficient, f_{wm} , of the membrane for different fluids used in the present study are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—FRICTIONAL COEFFICIENT, f_{wm} , FOR WATER AND AMMONIUM SALT SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT 35°

Concentration (mol. l ⁻¹)	$f_{wm} \times 10^{-8}$ (dyn. sec. cm ⁻¹ . mol ⁻¹)			
	Water	NH ₄ NO ₃	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	(NH ₄) ₃ PO ₄
Water	3.46			
Salt				
0.005	4.88	5.75	6.89	
0.01	6.03	7.05	7.51	
0.02	6.57	7.66	7.89	
0.04	7.26	8.12	8.24	
0.06	7.76	8.49	8.54	
0.08	8.18	8.95	9.14	

Fig. 2. Variation of J_v with ΔP at 35°.

—x—x— Water
 —o—o— 0.08M Ammonium nitrate solution
 —Δ—Δ— 0.08M Ammonium sulphate solution
 —□—□— 0.08M Ammonium phosphate solution

Table 3 shows that the filtration coefficient decreases as one goes from NH₄NO₃ to (NH₄)₃PO₄.

Table 4 shows that the value of f_{wm} when pure water flows, is less than that of f_{wm} when electrolyte

solution flows through the membrane. It is inferred from this that the resistance offered by the soil to water in its penetration through the membrane is less than that offered to the electrolyte solution. The variation of f_{wm} with salt concentration is shown in Fig. 3. The figure shows that at higher concentration of the electrolyte f_{wm} tends to become independent of concentration.

Fig. 3. Dependence of f_{wm} upon concentration of the electrolyte at 35°.

—○—○— Ammonium phosphate
 —△—△— Ammonium sulphate
 —□—□— Ammonium nitrate

Evaluation of the average porosity of the soil membrane: The complex nature of the membrane porosity is due to the absence of straight capillaries. The liquid flows in a zig-zag path and the characterization of such a membrane is possible only in terms of $\frac{A}{l}$ from which the average porosity can be estimated. Under the action of the hydrostatic pressure or the electrical current, the rate of permeation will depend on the effective cross-sectional area A and the thickness of the membrane l . Because of the complex nature of the openings inside the membrane, it is not possible to determine the values of the above mentioned quantities. However, $\frac{A}{l}$, the membrane constant can be determined, in terms of which the permeation behaviour of any soil membrane can be expressed.

Now consider a membrane having n number of pores of equivalent radius ' r ' and effective length l . The effective cross-sectional area A of this membrane through which permeation occurs can be equated to

$$A = n\pi r^2$$

If k is the specific conductivity of the permeant, then the electrical conductance of the permeant can be written as⁸ :

$$K = \frac{n\pi r^2 k}{l} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$= \frac{A}{l} \cdot k \quad \dots (8)$$

Hence the membrane constant $\frac{A}{l} = \frac{K}{k}$... (9)

where K is the conductance of the membrane plus the solution, and k is the specific conductance of the solution determined by the usual conductivity measurements.

The membrane constant characterises the membrane but does not depend on the nature of the permeating solution, so long as the interaction between the permeant and membrane matrix is negligible and is not in a position to change the equivalent pore radius.

The values of the membrane constant obtained from the conductance data of different ammonium salt solutions are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—MEMBRANE CHARACTERISTICS OBTAINED FROM THE CONDUCTANCE MEASUREMENTS

Concentration (mol. l ⁻¹)	$K \times 10^6$ (mhos)	$k \times 10^6$ (mhos. cm ⁻¹)	$A/l \times 10$ (cm)
Salt: NH ₄ NO ₃			
0.005	0.20	0.8306	2.41
0.01	0.25	1.038	2.41
0.02	0.30	1.246	2.41
0.04	0.35	1.454	2.41
0.06	0.40	1.661	2.41
0.08	0.45	1.869	2.41
Salt: (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄			
0.005	0.25	1.038	2.41
0.01	0.30	1.246	2.41
0.02	0.35	1.454	2.41
0.04	0.40	1.661	2.41
0.06	0.45	1.869	2.41
0.08	0.55	2.284	2.41
Salt: (NH ₄) ₂ PO ₄			
0.005	0.30	1.246	2.41
0.01	0.40	1.661	2.41
0.02	0.45	1.869	2.41
0.04	0.50	2.077	2.41
0.06	0.55	2.284	2.41
0.08	0.60	2.492	2.41

Table 5 suggests that the soil membrane studied has the same value of A/l , i.e., 0.24 cm for all the solutions used. In the present study, the salt solutions are fairly dilute and the membrane constant appears to vary negligibly in the concentration range used here.

Taking viscosity for the solutions of ammonium nitrate, ammonium sulphate and ammonium phosphate as $2.87 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{-3}$ p; $2.89 \pm 0.03 \times 10^{-3}$ p and $2.96 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-3}$ p respectively, the average pore radii for different solutions at different

concentrations and at 35° were calculated by using the following expression⁸ :

$$\left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta P}\right)_{\Delta\phi=0} = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} = \frac{A}{l} \cdot \frac{r^3}{8\eta}$$

or

$$r = \left(\frac{8\eta(J_v/\Delta P)_{\Delta\phi=0}}{A/l}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad \dots (10)$$

where

η is the viscosity of the permeant,

J_v is the volume flux,

ΔP is the pressure difference in cm of the permeant and

$\Delta\phi$ the electrical potential difference.

The pore radii thus calculated are given in Table 6.

TABLE 6—AVERAGE PORE RADII OF THE SOIL MEMBRANE

Concentration (mol. l ⁻¹)	Pore radius (× 10 ⁸ cm)
Salt : Ammonium nitrate	
0.005	2.62
0.01	2.35
0.02	2.25
0.04	2.14
0.06	2.07
0.08	2.02
Salt : Ammonium sulphate	
0.005	2.42
0.01	2.19
0.02	2.10
0.04	2.03
0.06	1.99
0.08	1.94
Salt : Ammonium phosphate	
0.005	2.24
0.01	2.14
0.02	2.09
0.04	2.04
0.06	2.01
0.08	1.94

Table 6 shows that the pore radius somewhat decreases with increasing concentration for all the salts studied here. This may be attributed to the change in the electrical double layer at the solution-soil interface caused by electrostatic interactions.

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